

Vascular Obstruction Scoring on Dual-energy CT, Cone-beam CT and Digital Subtraction Angiography: Correlation with Invasive Hemodynamics in Chronic Thromboembolic Pulmonary Hypertension

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Rationale and Objectives: To evaluate correlations between a standardized vascular obstruction score and invasive hemodynamic parameters in chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension (CTEPH), using dual-energy CT (DECT), cone-beam CT (CBCT), and digital subtraction angiography (DSA).

Materials and Methods: In this retrospective single-center study, 109 patients with CTEPH underwent DECT, CBCT, and DSA within a 3-month interval. A standardized vascular obstruction score was applied independently to each modality. Linear regression models were constructed to assess associations with mean pulmonary arterial pressure (mPAP), pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR), cardiac output (CO), and cardiac index (CI), quantified by adjusted R^2 . Score distributions were compared using Friedman and Wilcoxon tests, and interobserver agreement was assessed with Cohen's κ .

Results: DSA demonstrated the highest degree of association with mPAP and PVR among the evaluated modalities (adjusted $R^2 = 0.089$ and 0.126), followed by DECT (0.075 and 0.098) and CBCT (0.050 and 0.062). DSA also correlated with CO and CI. Mean obstruction scores differed significantly across modalities ($p < 0.001$), with DECT yielding higher values than CBCT ($p < 0.001$) and DSA ($p < 0.001$). Interobserver agreement was highest for CBCT ($\kappa = 0.76$) and DECT ($\kappa = 0.74$), and lowest for DSA ($\kappa = 0.57$). None of the modalities correlated significantly with NYHA class or 6MWD.

Conclusion: A unified morphologic vascular obstruction score applied across DECT, CBCT, and DSA demonstrates reproducible associations with invasive hemodynamic parameters in CTEPH. While not a replacement for right heart catheterization, it provides a standardized framework for multimodality assessment and may support methodological integration across imaging modalities.

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Critical Relevance Statement: This study presents a systematic application of a unified vascular obstruction scoring system across dual-energy CT, cone-beam CT, and digital subtraction angiography in patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. The results demonstrate significant correlations with invasive hemodynamic parameters, with dual-energy CT and cone-beam CT providing higher reproducibility than angiography. These findings support the use of a standardized scoring framework to enable consistent multimodality assessment, improve reproducibility in structured multimodality imaging assessment, and facilitate cross-institutional comparisons in chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension.

Key Words: Angiography; Cone-beam computed tomography; Dual-energy; Hemodynamics; Pulmonary hypertension.

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Abbreviations: BPA Balloon Pulmonary Angioplasty, CBCT Cone-Beam CT, CI Cardiac Index, CO Cardiac Output, CTEPH Chronic Thromboembolic Pulmonary Hypertension, CTA CT pulmonary angiography, DECT Dual-Energy CT, DSA Digital Subtraction Angiography, NYHA New York Heart Association, mPAP Mean Pulmonary Arterial Pressure, PEA Pulmonary endarterectomy, PVR Pulmonary Vascular Resistance, V/Q ventilation-perfusion, WU Wood units, 6MWD 6-Minute Walking Distance

Key Points

- Study applying a unified vascular obstruction scoring system across DECT, CBCT, and DSA in CTEPH.
- All three modalities demonstrated statistically significant associations with invasive hemodynamic parameters.
- DECT and CBCT achieved higher interobserver agreement than DSA.
- DSA demonstrated the highest degree of association with mPAP and PVR among the evaluated modalities.
- A standardized scoring framework enables consistent multimodality assessment and may support structured imaging evaluation in CTEPH.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension (CTEPH) is a rare (annual incidence of 3–5/100,000) and potentially fatal condition classified within group 4 pulmonary hypertension (1). It is defined by persistent obstruction of the pulmonary arteries, with a mean pulmonary arterial pressure (mPAP) > 20 mmHg and a pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR) > 2 Wood units (WU) despite more than 3 months of effective anticoagulation (1–5). Although potentially curable, CTEPH remains underdiagnosed due to nonspecific symptoms and complex imaging findings (6,7). Currently, initial screening typically involves ventilation–perfusion (V/Q) scintigraphy. If positive, advanced imaging is required to confirm the diagnosis and assess the disease extent. It also informs treatment eligibility for pulmonary endarterectomy (PEA), balloon pulmonary angioplasty (BPA), or targeted medical therapy (8–10). In this context, an unmet need is to clarify how morphologic obstruction seen on imaging reflects hemodynamic severity, the

key determinant of symptoms, prognosis, and therapy in CTEPH.

In this setting, imaging serves not only to confirm the diagnosis but also to define the extent, distribution, and morphology of pulmonary vascular obstruction. These features contribute to therapeutic decision-making (10). While CT pulmonary angiography (CTA) is widely used, its performance declines at distal arterial levels, particularly in patients being evaluated for BPA (8,9,11). Digital subtraction pulmonary angiography (DSA) is traditionally regarded as the reference standard for lesion identification, but it provides limited functional information (10). Dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography (DECT) enables assessment of both vascular anatomy and parenchymal perfusion through iodine maps (9,10,12). Cone-beam CT pulmonary angiography (CBCT), performed during DSA procedures, provides high-resolution volumetric imaging and is increasingly used for treatment planning (13–16). Unlike CT, the clinical value of applying morphologic scores to CBCT or DSA is less evident, as invasive hemodynamics are obtained in the same session. Their main potential lies in providing methodological consistency across modalities.

Previous studies reported only modest correlations between CT-derived obstruction scores and invasive hemodynamics (17–20). To date, no studies have systematically compared vascular obstruction scores across DECT, CBCT, and DSA in relation to invasive hemodynamic parameters. This study addresses this gap by evaluating and correlating these imaging scores in a single CTEPH cohort. Using a scoring framework adapted from prior work, particularly Abozeed et al., this study evaluates the feasibility, reproducibility, and hemodynamic associations of a unified, modality-agnostic morphologic score applied across DECT, CBCT, and DSA in a single CTEPH cohort (17). We hypothesized that a unified obstruction score would show measurable associations with invasive hemodynamics across modalities and improve reproducibility in multimodality CTEPH assessment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

This retrospective single-center study was conducted at a tertiary academic institution with a dedicated multidisciplinary CTEPH unit. Institutional review board approval was obtained and informed consent was waived. This study adheres to the STROBE Statement and the Helsinki Declaration. Patients with CTEPH evaluated between January 2017 and June 2022 were retrospectively identified. Inclusion criteria were patients aged ≥ 18 years who underwent DECT, CBCT, and DSA within a maximum interval of 3 months as part of their CTEPH work-up. Patients were excluded if any imaging interval exceeded 3 months, if DECT was performed using single-energy acquisition, if CBCT was not acquired during the DSA session, or if the patient had previously undergone PEA or BPA treatment.

Hemodynamic and Clinical Variables

All patients underwent right heart catheterization (RHC) as part of routine diagnostic work-up on the same day as the DSA/CBCT study. Recorded variables included mean mPAP, PVR, cardiac output (CO) and cardiac index (CI). Functional status was evaluated using the NYHA functional class and the distance during the 6-minute walking distance (6MWD).

Imaging Protocols

DECT was performed using a dual-source CT system (SOMATOM Definition Flash[®], Siemens Healthineers[®], Erlangen, Germany). Acquisition parameters included 80 kV and 140 kV tube voltages, 100–300 mAs, pitch 0.6, and a rotation time of 0.25 s. Bolus tracking was used with 75–85 mL of iodinated contrast (Ultravist[®] 370, Bayer, Leverkusen, Germany), followed by a 30 mL saline flush at 5 mL/s. Images were reconstructed using ADMIRE[®] (Siemens Healthineers[®], Erlangen, Germany) (Level 3) with Br40 (mediastinal) and Br64 (lung) kernels. Axial series were generated with 1 mm slice thickness for mediastinal, lung, and DECT iodine maps.

CBCT was performed in a flat-panel angiography suite (ArtisQ[®], Siemens Healthineers[®], Erlangen, Germany) using an Angled 5Fr pigtail catheter (Performa[®], Merit Medical[®], South Jordan, UT, USA) placed in the main pulmonary artery via right internal jugular venous access using a 5Fr/10cm vascular sheath (Pinnacle[®], Terumo[®], Tokyo, Japan). A total of 80 mL of contrast (70 mL iodinated contrast + 10 mL saline) was injected at 8–10 mL/s using a dual-chamber injector. Acquisitions were performed with a 5sDR CBCT preset (100–120 kV, 100–300 mA, 5-second rotation, 30×40 cm FOV). Reconstructions included axial, multiplanar, and 3D reformats.

DSA was performed immediately following CBCT using the same access and equipment as CBCT. Selective pulmonary angiograms were acquired in standard posteroanterior,

lateral (90°), and oblique (45°) projections. Each run involved 20–25 mL of iodinated contrast injected at 10–12 mL/s, with a 2-second delay, at six frames/second, 60–80 kV and 200–400 mAs.

Image Interpretation

All studies were interpreted independently by two radiologists per modality, blinded to all hemodynamic and clinical results. All readers met before reading started to unify the interpretation criteria. DECT images were reviewed by two board-certified chest radiologists (5 and 7 years of experience), and CBCT and DSA by two board-certified interventional radiologists (4 and 7 years of experience). A washout period of at least one month was observed between CBCT and DSA readings. DECT studies were evaluated using both the angiographic images and the iodine perfusion maps in an integrated fashion to support lesion identification and classification. CBCT images were assessed using multiplanar reformats optimized for visualization of the pulmonary arterial tree. DSA was reviewed using standard anteroposterior, lateral (ipsilateral 90°), and oblique (ipsilateral 45°) projections, utilizing both subtracted and unsubtracted image series. All images were reviewed using the Syngo.via[®] software (Siemens Healthineers[®], Erlangen, Germany). For all angiographic images (DECT, CBCT, and DSA), the pulmonary arteries were evaluated bilaterally at five anatomical levels: trunk, main, lobar, segmental, and subsegmental. Lesions were classified as present or absent, and if present, further categorized as either stenosis or occlusion. In the case of DSA and DECT, either angiography perfusion or iodine perfusion maps were used in conjunction with the angiographic series to support and enhance the identification of affected areas. Subsegmental arteries were scored only when opacification and image quality allowed confident evaluation; otherwise, they were excluded from analysis. No repeat readings were performed to assess intraobserver reproducibility.

A standardized vascular obstruction score was applied by assigning a fixed weight to each affected anatomical level: trunk = 5, main = 4, lobar = 3, segmental = 2, and subsegmental = 1. The maximum achievable score per patient was 85 points, based on evaluation of 1 trunk, 2 main, 5 lobar, 19 segmental, and 19 subsegmental arteries. Lesions were categorized as either stenosis or occlusion, based on their angiographic appearance. Occlusions, defined as complete absence of contrast opacification with no distal flow, contributed a cumulative score including the affected artery and all its downstream branches. Stenoses, defined as any degree of luminal narrowing with preserved distal contrast flow, contributed only the score corresponding to the affected level. Lesions were scored individually according to their level, and scores were aggregated into a single composite value per patient and per modality. The average score of both readers was used for correlation analyses. This scoring framework was adapted from the model proposed by

Abozeed et al. (17) and refined to reflect both anatomical distribution and lesion severity.

Statistical Analysis

Linear regression models were constructed to explore the relationship between imaging scores and continuous hemodynamic variables, incorporating the mean score of both readers per modality. Model assumptions were tested. No heteroscedasticity was observed (Breusch–Pagan $p > 0.05$). Residuals were not normally distributed in several models (Shapiro–Wilk $p < 0.05$), though this is mitigated by the sample size ($n = 109$). Associations were quantified using adjusted R^2 values. Differences in obstruction scores between DECT, CBCT, and DSA were assessed using the Friedman test, with post hoc Wilcoxon signed-rank tests and Bonferroni correction. Interobserver agreement was assessed using Cohen's κ statistic. The number and distribution of lesions, occlusions, and stenosis subtypes were quantified by modality, reader, and arterial level. Statistical significance was defined as a two-sided p -value < 0.05 . Analyses were performed in R (v.2024.12, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

RESULTS

Baseline Characteristics

Of the 209 patients assessed, 109 met all inclusion criteria and were included in the analysis (Fig 1). The most common reason for exclusion was an interval > 3 months between imaging modalities ($n = 42$). The cohort included 60 men (53.1%) with a mean age of 60.1 years (SD 16.1). Mean time between DECT and the CBCT/DSA session was 26.5 days (SD 28.2). Mean mPAP was 34.0 mmHg (SD 14.1), and 56 patients (51.4%) were in NYHA functional class III (Table 1).

Lesion Detection and Distribution

A total of 2943 pulmonary arteries were evaluated per imaging modality, comprising 109 trunk arteries, 218 main arteries, 545 lobar arteries, and 2071 segmental arteries (Fig 2). CBCT identified the highest number of arteries with chronic thromboembolic lesions (2400 by reader 1 and 2453 by reader 2), followed by DECT (1968 and 2093) and DSA (2141 and 1661). The detailed anatomical distribution of detected lesions is presented in Table 2.

Figure 1. Flowchart of patient selection and study design.

TABLE 1. Baseline Patient Characteristics

	n = 109
Age, years	60.8 (16.1)
BMI, kg/m ²	28.3 (7.9)
Sex, male	60 (53.1)
Time between DECT and DSA/ CBCT, days	26.5 (28.2)
NYHA-FC	
I	4 (3.7)
II	28 (25.7)
III	56 (51.4)
IV	21 (19.3)
Invasive treatment, yes	58 (53.2)
BPA	23 (21.1)
PEA	36 (33.0)
6MWD, meters	420 (129)
mPAP, mmHg	34 (14.1)
PVR, WU	5.1 (4.9)
Cardiac output, L/min	4.3 (1.3)
Cardiac index, L/min/m ²	2.3 (0.6)

Categorical variables are expressed in total values (%) and continuous variables in mean (SD).

DECT: dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography. DSA: digital subtraction pulmonary angiography. CBCT: cone-beam CT pulmonary angiography. BPA: balloon pulmonary angioplasty. PEA: pulmonary endarterectomy. 6MWD: 6 min walking distance. BMI: body mass index. mPAP: mean pulmonary artery pressure. NYHA-FC: New York Heart Association functional class. PVR: pulmonary vascular resistance.

Vascular Obstruction Scores per Modality

The mean vascular obstruction score was highest for DECT (26.3), followed by CBCT (24.1) and DSA (22.9). These differences were statistically significant (Friedman $\chi^2 = 20.69$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$). Post hoc Wilcoxon tests with Bonferroni correction confirmed significant differences between DECT and CBCT ($p < 0.001$), as well as between DECT and DSA

($p < 0.001$), while no significant difference was found between CBCT and DSA (adjusted $p = 1.00$).

Correlation Between Imaging Scores and Hemodynamic Parameters

DECT scores significantly correlated with mPAP ($\beta = 0.193$, $p = 0.004$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.075$), PVR ($\beta = 0.073$, $p < 0.001$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.098$), and CI ($\beta = -0.007$, $p = 0.028$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.040$), but not with CO ($\beta = -0.008$, $p = 0.210$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.006$). CBCT scores correlated with mPAP ($\beta = 0.155$, $p = 0.017$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.050$) and PVR ($\beta = 0.057$, $p = 0.009$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.062$), but not with CO ($\beta = -0.006$, $p = 0.370$, adjusted $R^2 = -0.002$) or CI ($\beta = -0.004$, $p = 0.330$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.010$). DSA scores demonstrated the strongest associations, with significant correlations to mPAP ($\beta = 0.212$, $p = 0.002$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.089$), PVR ($\beta = 0.084$, $p < 0.001$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.126$), CI ($\beta = -0.008$, $p = 0.007$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.070$), and CO ($\beta = -0.020$, $p = 0.002$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.091$).

None of the modalities showed significant correlations with 6MWD (DECT $\beta = 1.06$, $p = 0.111$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.017$; CBCT $\beta = 0.072$, $p = 0.910$, adjusted $R^2 = -0.011$; DSA $\beta = 0.675$, $p = 0.324$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.000$) or NYHA functional class (DECT $\beta = 0.005$, $p = 0.142$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.011$; CBCT $\beta = 0.003$, $p = 0.377$, adjusted $R^2 = -0.002$; DSA $\beta = 0.002$, $p = 0.500$, adjusted $R^2 = -0.005$). Complete regression results are presented in [Table 3](#) and [Figure 3](#).

Interobserver Agreement

The highest interobserver agreement was observed for CBCT ($\kappa = 0.76$), followed closely by DECT ($\kappa = 0.74$), and the lowest for DSA ($\kappa = 0.57$). Agreement was strongest at proximal arterial levels, with excellent κ values at the main arteries across all modalities (range 0.80–0.86). Agreement declined at more distal levels, reaching moderate values at the subsegmental level ($\kappa = 0.53$ –0.64) ([Table 4](#) and [Fig 4](#)).

Figure 2. Representative examples of chronic thromboembolic lesions across imaging modalities. (a) Axial DECT showing an eccentric chronic thrombus (arrow) within the right main pulmonary artery. (b) DSA demonstrating a ring-like stenosis (arrow) in the left lower lobar artery. (c) Coronal CBCT revealing an intraluminal band (arrow) in the superior segmental branch of the left lower lobe. (d) Axial iodine map from DECT depicting multiple subsegmental perfusion defects (arrows).

TABLE 2. Lesion Detection and Subtype Distribution by Modality

	DECT		CBCT		DSA	
	R1	R2	R1	R2	R1	R2
Arteries with lesions	1968	2093	2400	2452	2141	1661
Main branches	11	17	11	10	1	1
Lobar branches	111	165	120	115	80	93
Segmental branches	1144	1188	1345	1398	1224	1033
Subsegmental involvement	702	723	924	929	836	534

DECT: dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography. **DSA:** digital subtraction pulmonary angiography. **CBCT:** cone-beam CT pulmonary angiography.

TABLE 3. Linear Regression Results

	β (SE)	n = 109	
		<i>p</i> -value	Adj R ²
CO			
DECT	-0.008 (0.007)	0.210	0.006
CBCT	-0.006 (0.006)	0.370	-0.002
DSA	-0.020 (0.006)	0.002	0.091
CI			
DECT	-0.007 (0.003)	0.03	0.040
CBCT	-0.004 (0.003)	0.130	0.010
DSA	-0.008 (0.003)	0.007	0.070
mPAP			
DECT	0.193 (0.066)	0.004	0.075
CBCT	0.155 (0.064)	0.017	0.050
DSA	0.212 (0.067)	0.002	0.089
PVR			
DECT	0.073 (0.022)	0.001	0.098
CBCT	0.057 (0.021)	0.009	0.062
DSA	0.084 (0.022)	0.001	0.126
6MWD			
DECT	1.06 (0.659)	0.111	0.017
CBCT	0.072 (0.641)	0.910	-0.011
DSA	0.675 (0.680)	0.324	0.000
NYHA-FC			
DECT	0.005 (0.003)	0.142	0.011
CBCT	0.003 (0.003)	0.377	-0.002
DSA	0.002 (0.003)	0.500	-0.005

DECT: dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography. DSA: digital subtraction pulmonary angiography. CBCT: cone-beam CT pulmonary angiography. mPAP: mean pulmonary artery pressure. PVR: pulmonary vascular resistance. CI: Cardiac Index. CO: Cardiac Output. 6MWD: 6-minute walking distance. NYHA-FC: New York Health Association Functional Class.

β = regression coefficient. SE= standard error. Adj. R²= adjusted R-squared. Significance (*p*-value < 0.05) demonstrated in **bold**.

DISCUSSION

This study shows that a standardized vascular obstruction score applied across DECT, CBCT, and DSA is associated with invasive hemodynamic parameters in CTEPH. All modalities demonstrated significant associations with mPAP and PVR, with DSA showing the highest degree of association, followed by DECT and CBCT. Interobserver

agreement was higher for DECT and CBCT than for DSA, and mean scores differed significantly across modalities, with DECT systematically producing higher values. These findings suggest that a unified scoring system can translate morphologic burden into reproducible metrics applicable to structured multimodality assessment, supporting more consistent morphologic characterization and comparison across imaging modalities.

While several prior studies have explored CT- or DECT-based obstruction scores and their relationship to invasive hemodynamics, these investigations were limited to single imaging techniques and did not assess whether a common scoring framework could be applied reproducibly across different modalities. In contrast, the present study focuses on the systematic application of a unified morphologic obstruction score across DECT, CBCT, and DSA in the same CTEPH cohort, enabling direct comparison of score distributions, interobserver agreement, and hemodynamic associations across modalities. Abozeed et al. proposed one of the most structured approaches, integrating vascular obstruction and segmental perfusion defects, with modest correlations reported for mPAP and PVR ($r = 0.36$ and $r = 0.34$, respectively) (17). Given its clarity, clinical feasibility, and prior validation, we intentionally adopted the morphologic component of their score as the basis for our framework, in order to enable direct comparison and reproducible application across DECT, CBCT, and DSA. Unlike Abozeed et al., who analyzed DECT exclusively, our study included perfusion assessment during DECT interpretation while maintaining a standardized morphologic scoring system to allow comparison across modalities. Leone et al. described a CTPA-based score incorporating central occlusion and indirect signs, with correlation coefficients of ($r = 0.58$ for mPAP, $r = 0.63$ for PVR). However, their model was not designed for reproducibility across techniques (18). Takagi et al. found a correlation of $r = 0.59$ with mPAP using a DECT vascular obstruction index in a smaller cohort. At the same time, Meinel et al. reported a significant association with mPAP using iodine map quantification, though correlation with PVR was limited (19,21). In our cohort, DSA showed the highest degree of association with both mPAP and PVR (adjusted R² = 0.089 and 0.126), followed by DECT (adjusted R² = 0.075 and 0.098) and CBCT

Figure 3. Correlation between vascular obstruction scores and hemodynamic parameters by imaging modality. Scatterplots show the relationship between mean vascular obstruction scores and mPAP (top row), PVR (second row), CI (third row), and CO (bottom row) for DECT (left column), CBCT (middle column), and DSA (right column). Each plot includes a linear regression line with 95%CI. Statistically significant positive correlations were observed between obstruction scores and both mPAP and PVR, particularly with DSA-derived scores. CI and CO demonstrated negative trends across modalities.

TABLE 4. Interobserver Agreement for Lesion Detection by Modality and Arterial Level

	DECT (κ)	CBCT (κ)	DSA (κ)
	n = 2943		
Overall	0.74	0.76	0.57
By arterial level			
Main branches	0.80	0.82	0.81
Lobar branches	0.75	0.77	0.60
Segmental branches	0.68	0.70	0.58
Subsegmental	0.53	0.64	0.54

κ: Cohen’s kappa coefficient. DECT: dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography. DSA: digital subtraction pulmonary angiography. CBCT: cone-beam CT pulmonary angiography.

Cohen’s κ values are presented for each modality. Values > 0.75 are shown in **bold** to indicate excellent agreement. Slight: 0.01–0.20; Fair: 0.21–0.40; Moderate: 0.41–0.60; Substantial: 0.61–0.80; Almost perfect: > 0.81.

(adjusted $R^2 = 0.050$ and 0.062). Interobserver agreement, which was not assessed in most previous studies, was highest for DECT and CBCT, supporting their value as reproducible tools in multimodal evaluation. This likely reflects the standardized, cross-sectional nature of both

modalities, which allows consistent interpretation across readers. In contrast, DSA is projection-dependent and more susceptible to variability in angulation, injection timing, and overlap, particularly at distal levels. The relatively high κ despite differences in absolute lesion counts, especially at the lobar level, likely reflects the predominance of negative cases, which can inflate agreement. In such settings, high κ values may primarily reflect concordant classification of normal vessels rather than perfect agreement in the identification or characterization of abnormal segments, and should therefore be interpreted in conjunction with lesion distribution and absolute counts.

The variation in correlation strength across modalities may be explained not only by differences in spatial resolution or image quality, but also by the specific role each technique plays within the anatomical and functional spectrum of CTEPH. Although mean vascular obstruction scores were relatively similar across modalities, stronger differences in correlation likely reflect extreme cases, where discordance in distal disease detection between modalities had a greater impact on the hemodynamic association. This suggests that outlier patients with disproportionate distal burden may drive part of the variability observed between DECT, CBCT, and DSA. DSA provided the highest degree of associations with mPAP and PVR in our cohort, likely due to its capacity to

Figure 4. Interobserver agreement by arterial level and imaging modality. DECT (blue), CBCT (red), and DSA (green). Agreement was highest at proximal levels ($\kappa > 0.80$) and declined distally. Substantial to excellent agreement was maintained by DECT and CBCT down to the segmental level, while DSA demonstrated greater variability and lower reproducibility overall. Dashed horizontal line indicates threshold for excellent agreement ($\kappa=0.75$).

depict subtle flow-related abnormalities in real time, especially in subsegmental vessels. However, it lacks perfusion information and shows lower interobserver agreement. DECT offered a balanced profile, with high reproducibility and strong correlations, possibly enhanced by the combined interpretation of axial anatomy and iodine maps. This is consistent with results by Leone et al., who reported solid correlations using a CT-based obstruction score that included both anatomical and functional surrogates (18). CBCT, although less explored in this context, showed intermediate performance and high reader consistency, supporting its value as an intraprocedural tool despite a more limited field-of-view (16,22,23). Hoey et al., who evaluated DECT perfusion patterns, reported no significant correlation with mPAP or PVR, highlighting the limitations of visual perfusion analysis when used in isolation (24). Renapurkar et al focused on the prognostic role of DECT scores after surgery, but did not evaluate their correlation with baseline hemodynamics (20). Our design, in contrast, focused on pre-treatment evaluation and standardized scoring across modalities.

Moreover, phase-contrast MRI has been explored as a noninvasive alternative. Kreitner et al. developed a high-temporal-resolution PC-MRI model that achieved excellent agreement with invasively measured mPAP and acceptable correlation with PVR ($R^2 = 0.89$ and 0.79 , respectively) (25). However, its use remains limited by availability, operator expertise, and integration within standard CTEPH

algorithms. Lastly, although our score is morphologic and does not directly assess microvasculopathy, we sought to account for the most distal evaluable disease by assigning specific weight to subsegmental arteries. Peripheral, subpleural abnormalities, such as vessel pruning or wedge-shaped perfusion defects, were consistently classified as subsegmental involvement on DSA and iodine maps, following the definitions proposed by Onishi et al. and Miwa et al. (26,27). While this approach does not capture true microvascular remodeling, it offers a structured surrogate for distal vascular burden. Notably, despite this inherent limitation, the obstruction score demonstrated reproducible associations with hemodynamic parameters across modalities. Future developments, such as photon-counting CT, may enable more precise evaluation of distal vasculature, as suggested by Remy-Jardin et al. (28).

From a clinical standpoint, these findings support the consideration of structured morphologic scoring as part of routine imaging assessment of CTEPH, particularly in centers with access to multiple techniques. Pulmonary hemodynamics in CTEPH are influenced by multiple anatomical and physiological factors, of which morphologic vascular obstruction represents one component. Moreover, although identical scoring rules are applied, the obstruction score reflects overall morphologic disease burden rather than identical lesion depiction across imaging techniques. For example, a low score (e.g., 2) indicates limited involvement

of a small number of affected vessels, regardless of modality. Given differences in field of view, spatial resolution, and perfusion information, similar scores across DECT, CBCT, and DSA should be interpreted as representing comparable overall burden rather than lesion-by-lesion equivalence, and are best suited for longitudinal within-modality assessment and standardized cross-modality communication. DECT, combining cross-sectional anatomy and iodine-based perfusion, offers a practical noninvasive option that provides a reproducible morphologic description in relation to invasive hemodynamic measurements. CBCT, despite its more limited spatial coverage, may be useful as an adjunct during BPA procedures, especially in centers initiating their BPA programs (29). Moreover, the correlation observed with DSA supports its continued relevance as a reference imaging technique in this population (30). In this context, a unified morphologic scoring approach applied across modalities could facilitate more consistent anatomical characterization and procedural discussion, in multidisciplinary CTEPH conferences. The systematic application of a standardized, modality-agnostic vascular obstruction score may facilitate structured multidisciplinary discussion by enabling consistent, anatomy-based stratification of disease burden across imaging techniques, while also supporting objective longitudinal monitoring of morphologic disease burden over time, and facilitating meaningful comparisons across time-points and institutions. Additionally, in settings where RHC is not readily available, the morphologic obstruction score may provide a standardized morphologic descriptor related to invasive hemodynamic findings, potentially supporting standardized communication of morphologic disease burden across centers. Future studies should explore the potential of this scoring framework for standardized longitudinal morphologic assessment and multicenter implementation.

This study has several limitations. First, its retrospective, single-center design may limit generalizability. Although all patients underwent all three imaging modalities, the order and timing were not uniform, which could introduce variability in lesion appearance and perfusion status. Also, the requirement that all three imaging modalities be available within a three-month interval selected a specific subset of patients, typically evaluated at a tertiary referral center, potentially overrepresenting more advanced or complex disease. This may have influenced lesion distribution and hemodynamic associations, and the score may behave differently in less selected or earlier-stage CTEPH populations. Moreover, DSA interpretation is inherently subjective and dependent on acquisition angles, which may explain the lower interobserver agreement despite strong hemodynamic correlation. Also, while we selected a morphologic score that was applicable across modalities, it may not capture other relevant dimensions such as distal vasculopathy or collateral flow, which could impact clinical outcomes. Furthermore, although our study did not include comparison with V/Q scintigraphy, which remains the recommended screening tool for CTEPH, future studies could explore how perfusion

defects on V/Q relate to morphologic obstruction scores across imaging modalities. Also, intraobserver reproducibility was not assessed, as repeat readings were not performed. Subsegmental arteries were evaluated only when opacification allowed confident interpretation, which may have introduced variability. Finally, the predominance of negative vessels may have inflated κ values despite discrepancies in absolute lesion counts.

CONCLUSION

Our findings demonstrate that a unified morphologic vascular obstruction score can be consistently applied across DECT, CBCT, and DSA, showing reproducible associations with invasive hemodynamic measurements. While not yet ready for routine clinical integration, this framework may serve as a standardized tool for comparative research, multicenter studies, and longitudinal assessment of CTEPH burden.

CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Isabel Blanco: Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ivan Vollmer:** Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Validation, Conceptualization. **Fernando M. Gómez:** Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Llúria Cornellàs:** Writing – review and editing, Data curation. **Joan A. Barberà:** Writing – review and editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Blanca Domenech-Ximenes:** Writing – review and editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Elena Serrano:** Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **Alfredo Páez-Carpio:** Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Fernando M. Gomez reports financial support was provided by Society of Spanish Medical Radiology (SERAM). If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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